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A Multi-Signature Scheme for Defending Malleability Attack on DeFi

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ABSTRACT Signatures are crucial in blockchain-based Decentralised Finance (DeFi) protocols because they ensure the security and integrity of transactions and smart contracts. Due to the weakness in the signature scheme, it is possible to carry out a malleability attack (MA) by changing the transaction ID (TxId) without affecting the transaction's actual content or validity. Currently, signature systems can only resist partial malleability attacks from multiple attack paths. This paper proposes an advanced multi-signature scheme (MSS) as a supplementary signature that integrates unmalleable transaction implementations. In MSS, the owners and block producers themselves generate the signature. MSS improves transaction efficiency by allowing many signers to establish a joint signature, which has piqued interest. Despite the method's complexity and time-consuming nature, this research has adapted MSS to the blockchain to safeguard against malleability attacks. By integrating it with several other optimisations, such as executing intermediate transactions using a hash function, MSS ensures complete resistance against malleability attacks. In comparison to baseline approaches, testbed simulations demonstrate scalability and 15% higher resistance against malleability attack success.

INDEX TERMS Blockchain, Digital signatures, Multi-Signatures, and Malleability Attacks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blockchain (BC) transactions as digital currency in FinTech enterprise applications are intended to verify the legal ownership of assets through the use of digital signatures [1]. For instance, J.P. Morgan, Santander, etc., banks are launching blockchain based capital markets, which involve large sums of money, various players, and extensive coordination. Usually, multiple parties are required to approve capital market transactions, making the approval process difficult [2]. Moreover, it can open up scopes of a malleability attack by exploiting an attacker who manipulates a transaction's cryptographic signature or other components to alter its transaction identifier (TxID) without changing its fundamental validity. This manipulation can disrupt the transaction flow, exploit smart contracts, and create vulnerabilities in DeFi systems [3]. It is also time-consuming, as each party must verify that the information matches the transaction history and follows participant regulations. Blockchain technology (BCT) is thought to reduce costs and streamline transactions between many parties in such a digital currency (DC). DC in

a permissioned network are resistant to counterfeiting; their malleability stems from the inability of a digital signature to self-sign. This malleability signifies that a signed transaction within DC can be modified to appear syntactically different yet retain semantic equivalence. Consequently, this characteristic is evident in current cryptocurrencies [4] like Bitcoin, Ethereum [5], Ripple [6], etc. These currencies face the challenge of malleability while the malleability of cryptocurrencies doesn't annul a transaction, it has attracted significant criticism for altering the transaction identifier *TxId*. For instance, the MtGox hack of 2014, stemming from Bitcoin's malleability attack, resulted in the theft of approximately 350 million worth of Bitcoin. Understanding and addressing these malleability attacks has received recent attention.

There are several ways that MA can happen, such as when an attacker gets Sybil nodes to change message M into \hat{M} ; \hat{M} gets mined in the normal transaction scenario, which causes M to be started again for fund withdrawal; and M_1 redeems M and is mined before M enters the blockchain, which makes M_1 invalid [7]. Some researchers are exploring

potential solutions using novel transaction implementations [8], [9]. For instance, an alternative hash value has been used in [8] for intermediate transaction for TxId excluding the input script. While the simplified hash can resolve most typical transactions, it is unable to avoid the malleability attack on existing protocols such as Bitcoin contracts [10]. The approach in [9] seeks to enhance wallet security by checking transactions with hash values and address balances. For a single transaction, it requires examining all relevant blocks to verify the address balance. This strategy is difficult for cryptocurrency platforms that need speedy approvals, such as securities registration, clearing, and settlement, since each block generally has 4000 transactions.

Alternative signature schemes proposed in [10], [11], aim to establish robust transaction frameworks within cryptocurrencies. There are two parameters used in the signature process of the new version of the ECDSA algorithm, which was written about in [12], [13], to protect it from weak randomness attacks. The proposed discrete non-malleable logarithm in [11] shows that the aggregate r-signature method works, which means the security is better. The integration of Segregated Witness [14] with the aggregate r-signature method notably strengthens Bitcoin's resilience against malleability attacks. However, the idea of transaction finality has not yet been put into practice despite these developments. Finality guarantees prompt confirmation after the transaction is finished. In [15], Liu et al. presented a combined signature technique that combines the aggregate technique described in [16] with the interactive incontestable signature. This scheme protect faked in random oracles, and is resistant to forgery. However, it still lacks resistance against MA through the signature script channel.

To sum up, stopping MA in DC transactions requires full protection across all channels and participation from multiple parties in three different situations [17]. With this method, multiple users may authenticate just one message and produce a collective signature that expresses their agreement. Joint signatures are usually the same length as single signatures and require only one verification using the public keys of participating signers. Thus, multi-signatures offer numerous advantages over digital signatures, including cheaper bandwidth, storage space, and verification speed [18].

This paper presents the concept of MSS, a multi-signature method that is designed to be easily used in unmalleable transactions. This technique's primary goal is to ensure DC's security and immediate redemption. This technique offers comprehensive strategies to manage transaction malleability in both online and offline transactions. MSS operates in both online and offline modes. In the offline mode, partial values are pre-computed without pre-knowledge of the message, and the final signature is generated upon the arrival of the message M in the online phase.

The remaining articles are presented in four more sections, which focus on their implications, methodologies, and evaluations. In order to make things clear, Section II offers a succinct summary of current developments in this field

and indicates the areas that require more study. Section III provides a comprehensive explanation of the overall process. Section V provides a concise summary of the experimental results, accompanied by graphical representations. Section VI provides the final analysis and summary of the implementation scenarios.

II. RELATED WORK

Signature systems are essential for guaranteeing the security, accuracy, and dependability of transactions in BCN, particularly in reducing the impact of MA. To ensure the authenticity of transactions and their immutability, researchers have undertaken significant work. For example, they've used ECDSA [19] and Schnorr Signatures [20]. This category offers a concise summary of the recent advancements in signature schemes aimed at mitigating MA, as well as identifying any existing research gaps.

A. MALLEABILITY ATTACK PROTECTION APPROACHES

To enhance transaction verification, the authors in [9] introduced a wallet to verify transaction hashes and address balances. Although it reduces the implementation effort, it is inappropriate in terms of scalability (i.e., rapid settlement) [21]. The authors in [8] used *hashhs* to sign the transaction data hash. However, this does not impact any changes made due to MA. At the moment, it *hashc* is utilised for verification and reference operations, whereas it *hashhs* is utilised for activity monitoring in adaptability attacks.

However, this strategy ignores malleability attacks on BC systems (e.g., bitcoin) and casts doubt on rapid confirmation. A few other researchers [22], [23] recommended altering transaction spending to prevent MA in DC protocols. For example, to protect 'Fuse' transactions from malleability attacks, NewSCS [24] used each party's secret and signature to improve a fair two-party protocol. In particular, the party A redeemed its transaction $Commit^A(in: M^A)$ by supplying the signature script containing $sig_B([Fuse^A])$ and the exposed secret Sr_A . In the same way, the other party's transaction $Fuse^B(in: Commit^B)$ redeemed its own transaction $Commit^B(in: M^B)$ using a signature script with the signature $sig_B([Fuse^B])$ and revealed secret. Both parties are required to undergo an additional iteration of the *Commit* protocol in order to disclose their secret values r_A or r_B , which significantly increases the complexity of NewSCS. Furthermore, it is imperative that we thoroughly analyse every protocol transaction for possible vulnerabilities related to malleability.

Likewise, a timed commitment approach is proposed in [25] to mitigate malleability for storing transactions through a deposit protocol. When the depositing method commits an unmalleable transaction, the compensation system permits the protocol to carry out all activities based on activated transactions. The idea behind this solution is to encourage additional protocols to protect malleability. A 'Fuse' transaction attack in the commitment scheme exposed the committer to at

TABLE 1: Research significance in comparing State-of-art

Technique	Defense for Maleability Attack	Attack Vectors Addressed	Scalability	Finality Guarantee	Compatibility	Complexity	Security Strength	Adoption
Segregated Witness	Partial	ScriptSig manipulation	High	No	High	Low	Moderate	High
Aggregate r-Signature	Partial	Rogue-key, k-sum issues	Moderate	No	Low	High	Moderate	Low
ECDSA	Weak (S-value manipulation possible)	Malleable s value rogue key	low	No	High	Low	Moderate	High
Alternative Hashing	Partial	Input script exclusions	High	No	High	Low	Moderate	Low
Interactive Incontestable Signature (IIS)	Moderate	Multi-party malleability	Moderate	Partial	Low	Moderate	High	Experimental
Multi-Signature Scheme (MSS)	Comprehensive	All major vectors	High	Yes	High	Moderate	High	Low

least double penalties by triggering 'Fuse' and 'Fuse', introducing another vulnerability. To prevent malleability attacks, a typical solution is to create signature schemes [12], [26], [27] while secret key management is the prime challenge. To prevent key theft and fraud, an EdDSA signature method for safe two-party transactions [26] used threshold signatures. Many digital coins (e.g., Cardano, Decred, etc.) use this protocol. Both parties can sign a normal transaction input using a conversational protocol, which makes the EdDSA signature valid.

A rogue node trying to construct a malleable transaction would need another interactive protocol round. The signature script can easily launch malleability attacks. Advanced technology, like post-quantum proof of work (PoW), was used in [27], [28] to use signing as proof of work. The system changes signing difficulty based on the likelihood of a correct signature [1] and uses signature verification for block rewards. Post-quantum PoW is secure and resistant to transaction malleability, although few coins use it. The existing signature scheme used in DC changes was proposed in [29] where they suggested the interactive inclusion of owners signatures in a non-repudiable manner to ensure the unforgeability and the dealer's incontestability. However, current practicality impedes the elimination of signatures between transaction parties. Table 1 provides a concise overview of the most prevalent signature schemes employed in malleability attacks, highlighting their major characteristics and notable distinctions from the proposed MSS method.

B. MULTI-SIGNATURE SCHEMES

In [30], a multi-signature protocol based on RSA is presented. Depending on the quantity of signers, several signatures are generated and verified. The authors of [31] also wrote about identity-based MSS based on the RSA assumption in the random oracle model. They said that their method for creating and verifying multiple signatures was faster than the one they had previously described. Consequently,

an improved version of identity-based MSS was proposed in [32] that minimises one interactive round. Also, in [33], the authors came up with a sequential aggregation signature scheme to make multi-signature more general. Every signer in this method signs a unique message, which is then tallied up in sequence. Aggregation of the signatures used in blockchain is proposed in [34] where multi-signature is used to ensure security and privacy in the IoT scenario.

Various signature systems, including multi-signature, are implemented to address security and efficiency issues. All of these strategies have demonstrated tremendous success in each scenario. As it shows, neither multi-signature techniques nor any other viable signature schemes have been implemented to protect against malleability attacks. This research focuses on examining a new multisignature technique that can effectively mitigate the malleability attack while also addressing the scalability of transactions. The suggested signature can be executed in two phases, namely offline and online. The offline mode emphasises precomputing resource-intensive activities to enhance real-time efficiency. For instance, producing shared group parameters and elliptic curve constants. Precomputing intermediate cryptographic values, including partial signature components, irrespective of particular transactions. Safeguarding these precomputed values for subsequent utilisation throughout the online period. Conversely, the online mode manages transaction-specific activities, guaranteeing rapid and safe real-time processing. It employs precomputed values alongside the transaction-specific hash to provide distinct signatures. Consolidating individual signatures into a unified group signature. Validating the proven aggregated signature to ascertain transaction validity and integrity. This division lowers computational burden during real-time processes, enhancing scalability and reducing latency in MSS.

III. METHODOLOGY

FIGURE 1: Transaction Process

A. OVERVIEW

In a blockchain network, there are a number of peers who are responsible for transaction approvals through consensus processes. However, in a private blockchain (e.g., Hyperledger Fabric [35]) only approved peers can join the network, and the approval process is maintained by a Certificate Authority (CA), which is ultimately responsible for managing the members. Every transaction is also validated through CA before execution, which is approved by a digital signature recorded earlier [36]. Many digital signature algorithms are used in different protocols; for example, the ECDSA is extensively utilised in Fabric to ensure the authenticity of transactions. During consensus, a 51% signature is required to approve the transactions, which is also known as proof-of-authority (PoA) [37]. The number of required signatures depends on the consensus policy. The overhead of signature verification will be proportional to the number of required signatures. The challenge here is that a higher number of required signatures will enhance security but reduce transaction efficiency, which means reduced scalability. Moreover, ECDSA can also be a potential source of malleability attacks (details in Section III-B).

The proposed MSS replaces ECDSA and incorporates a synchronisation step to safeguard the updated transaction method from malleability attacks. Figure 1 presents the overall MSS processes, including transaction execution steps. To understand the overall scenarios, let's assume the users $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ initiate transactions, the endorsing peer (P^e), and the consensus leader peer $P^l \in P_n^e$ lead the consensus processes and synchronise the signature schemes. To approve a block, it requires a N number of endorsers to join the consensus process and sign the ECDSA signature scheme, which can cause the malleability attack (details in Section III-B). In MSS, i the endorser may have a set of

FIGURE 2: Attack Model

children C_i who join the signature scheme and P^e role as P_i^p a parent of the endorser C_i . In ECDSA, the signature consists of two values, (r, s) , an attacker could modify the s value and submit a duplicate transaction with a new TxID. How the malleability attack can be performed has been presented in Section III-B. Mitigation approaches comprise six key steps, including parameter generation (PG), key generation (KG), key authentication (KA), signing (sign), key verification (KV), and verification (V), which are used to generate the signature generation and later on signing. The mitigation process for the proposed multi-signature scheme is stated in Section III-C. Similarly, more details about the signature generation and signing process are presented in Section III-D. The signing process in the MSS is divided into four key stages: *Initialisation*, *Commitment*, *Challenges*, and *Response*. These stages guarantee the integrity, efficiency, and non-malleability of the signature. The initialisation process establishes the cryptographic framework for signing; the commitment securely disseminates partial information, avoiding inappropriate disclosure of sensitive data, while the challenges link the commitments to the transaction being signed. The response produces partial signatures and consolidates them into a unified group signature.

B. POTENTIAL SOURCE OF MALLEABILITY ATTACKS IN DEFI

Within the realm of cryptocurrencies, malleability attacks against signature schemes are of significant importance since they have the potential to affect transaction processing and compromise the integrity of the blockchain. A signature technique can introduce malleability vulnerabilities in cryptocurrency systems in several ways. Figure 2 demonstrates the self-descriptive attacking framework. Typically, most of the cryptocurrencies use ECDSA-based systems; here the sender uses their private key to sign transactions, demonstrating

ownership and authorisation of the transaction. ECDSA is vulnerable to malleability attacks due to its intrinsic mathematical characteristics of elliptic curve encryption and the process of generating signatures. ECDSA can be susceptible to malleability attacks due to certain vulnerabilities.

- **Signature Generation:** In ECDSA, a signer generates a signature for a message by first generating a random value (i.e., a nonce) and then performing mathematical operations on this nonce and the message using their private key, which consists of two random integers r and s .
- **Transaction Signature:** The signature guarantees the individual possessing the private key has the ability to commence transactions. For example, two integers r and s are used to create signatures in the ECDSA scheme. However, validation necessitates checking both signatures (r, s) and $(r, BN - s)$.
- **Malleability Potentiality:** The s in an ECDSA signature is not inherently linked to the message or the private key in the same manner as the r value. An assailant can capitalise on this absence of binding by increasing the s value by a fixed factor (referred to as k) in order to generate a fresh signature while retaining the same r value. The resulting signature is deemed authentic for an altered message generated from the first message. An attacker can make more than one acceptable signature for the same message by changing the s value. Each signature will have a different s value. This ability to be changed can cause misunderstanding and could leave systems vulnerable that depend on signatures being unique, like cryptocurrency networks that verify transactions. This malleability can lead to confusion and potential vulnerabilities in systems relying on the uniqueness of signatures, such as transaction verification in cryptocurrency networks. For example, Alice signs a message with ECDSA, which makes a signature (r, s) . After stealing this signature, an attacker multiplies the s number by a constant k to make a new signature $(r, ks \bmod n)$, where n is the order of the elliptic curve. Even though they both have the same s value, they both sign the same letter.
- **DER-encoded ECDSA signatures:** Utilising the OpenSSL cryptographic library, most cryptocurrencies accept multiple formats besides the standardised DER encoding.
- **Signature script manipulation (scriptSig):** Malleability occurs when an attacker is able to modify a transaction's signature in such a way that it remains valid but produces a different transaction hash or identifier. The inclusion of the signature within *scriptSig* poses a challenge for signature schemes in cryptocurrencies. Transaction validation remains unaffected by certain modifications. For instance, operations like OP_{RDROP} leave the stack unaffected, and non-minimal encoding of push operations signifies equivalent data pushes. A

common change is to replace OP_0 , which encodes data length, with $OP_{\text{PUSHDATA2}}$, which encodes two bytes of data. Consequently, the resulting hex codes in the claiming script change from two bytes ($0 \times 48 \langle \text{Sig} \rangle 41 \langle \text{PubKey} \rangle$) to four bytes ($0 \times 4D4800 \langle \text{Sig} \rangle 4D4100 \langle \text{PubKey} \rangle$).

C. MULTI-SIGNATURE FOR DEFENDING MALLEABILITY ATTACK

A novel multi-signature technique is proposed to improve security, efficiency, and scalability, especially since it is capable of defending against malleability attacks. Proof of Possession (PoP) has been used to protect the transactions from malleability attacks. To reduce computational costs in PoP, Gamma signatures [38] have been used for the division of work between both online and offline. As a result, the computational challenge in online is improved compared to the CoSi signature scheme [39] and makes it difficult to forge using malleability attacks. We also scaled the idea using a spanning tree structure, which was CoSi-inspired. In summary, this solution aims to protect against k-sum and rogue-key threats while maximising online efficiency and scalability. The MSS depends on six key steps: parameter generation (PG), key generation (KG), key authentication (KA), signing (sign), key verification (KV), and verification (V).

1) Parameter Generation (PG)

PG is employed to build the cryptographic foundation for the multi-signature system. A collection of public parameters, comprising elliptic curve parameters and hash functions, is produced. These parameters delineate the mathematical framework and processes employed in the generation and validation of signatures. Guarantees that every party function within an integrated cryptographic framework. PG are required for the cryptographic operations. It generates Public parameters $(\mathcal{E}, G, n, H_1, H_2)$ where it defines the elliptic curve \mathcal{E} over a finite field \mathbb{F}_q , where q is a prime to select a generator point G on \mathcal{E} with a large prime order n and secure cryptographic hash functions H_1, H_2 for key hashing and signature binding, respectively.

2) Key Generation (KG)

It generates distinct key pairs (i.e., private key sk_i (kept secret) and public key pk_i (shared with the group)) for each participant. As Algorithm 2 presents, every participant creates a sk_i and calculates the associated pk_i utilising the specified \mathcal{E} . To generate keys, each participant i selects a private key sk_i uniformly at random from $[1, n - 1]$ and computes the corresponding public key $pk_i = sk_i \cdot G$. The private key remains confidential, whilst the pk_i is disseminated among the group. Guarantees the security and distinctiveness of each participant's cryptographic identification.

3) Key Authentication (KA):

It is employed to authenticate the validity of each participant's public key pk_1, pk_2, \dots, pk_n to prevent rogue-key attacks. Participants utilise $\text{PoP}_i = H_1(pk_i) \cdot x_i \cdot G$. and share PoP_i with other participants. The group jointly verifies PoP_i by $H_1(pk_i) \cdot G = \text{PoP}_i$ preventing the introduction of unauthorised keys. This phase is essential for preventing rogue-key attacks and fostering confidence among participants.

4) Signing (Sign)

Generating a group signature (\tilde{X}_{ij}) for a transaction is the key challenge, which is done through initialisation, commitment, challenges, and response which are detail at Algorithm 1 and Section III-D. As it is presented in Line 2 and Section III-C1, generates the parameters that are used to create both keys, sk, pk . It assists in producing partial signatures for a particular transaction. Every participant employs their sk_i to authenticate the transaction message or its hash. During the offline phase, participants precompute specific variables to mitigate computational burden during the signing procedure. The online phase integrates these precomputed values with transaction-specific data to generate partial signatures. Details of the signing processes are presented in Section III-D.

5) Key Verification (KV)

This process is used to confirm the validity of each participant's partial signature and its correspondence to a verified pk_i . Each partial signature is verified against its corresponding pk_i utilising the cryptographic settings. Invalid partial signatures are detected, allowing for a separation of malevolent actors. Guarantees that only legitimate contributions are consolidated into the final signature.

6) Verification (V)

To authenticate the combined signature and confirm the transaction. The combined signature is verified against the group's collective pk which is denoted as \tilde{X}_{ij} and the transaction message. If valid, the transaction is verified to be authentic and resistant to tampering. Guarantees the authenticity of the signature and its association with the transaction details. Details are presented in the commitment of Section III-D.

Furthermore, four hash functions, $H0, H1, H2, H3 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q$ have been employed, in which $(H0, H1)$ are treated as random oracles and $(H2, H3)$ is a one-way presentation of a hash function. Transaction signature processes are presented in detail in Section III-D and Section III-E presents more details about operational steps of the transactional approval process. Algorithm 1 describes the six phases in detail, including the signature procedures.

As shown in Algorithm 1 and 2, the PG process needs a session group (SG) (i.e., endorsers) of order q (a prime number with a K-bit) and a generator g_1 to come up with parameters $PM = (G, g_1, q)$. PM is used to generate a public key using a function $y = KG(PM)$ and sk is randomly peeked from $[0, q - 1]$.

Algorithm 1 Signing Algorithm

```

1: function SIGN( $G, q, m, \tau$ )
2:   for each phase  $i$  in PG, KG, KAg, Signing do
3:     Parameter  $PM \leftarrow (G, g_1, q) \triangleright$  group  $G$  of order
        $q$ 
4:     if  $PM$  then
5:       Call Algorithm 2
6:       Generate signature key  $(pk, sk)$ 
7:     end if
8:     if  $i > 1$  then
9:       Parse each public key  $pk_i$  as  $pk_i = (y_i, \pi_i) \triangleright$ 
        $i =$  number of signers
10:      Output aggregated public key  $\bar{PK} \leftarrow$ 
        $\prod_{pk_i \in PK} y_i$ 
11:    end if
12:    if Key generation succeeds then
13:      Call Algorithm 3 for Signature is generated
       for session  $\tau$ 
14:    end if
15:  end for
16: end function

```

Algorithm 2 Key Generation Process

```

1: Randomly pick  $sk \in [0, q - 1]$   $\triangleright$  private key
2: Compute  $y \leftarrow g_1^{sk}$   $\triangleright$  public key
3: Choose  $r \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ .
4: Compute  $a \leftarrow H1(g_1, g_1^r)$ 
5: Compute  $b \leftarrow H2(y)$ 
6: Compute  $d \leftarrow r \cdot a - b \cdot sk \pmod q$ 
7: Set  $\pi \leftarrow (a, d)$ 
8: Set  $pk \leftarrow (y, \pi)$ 
9: output  $(pk, sk)$ 

```

Consequently, Algorithm 2 generated (pk, sk) is used to form complex key by aggregating all the public keys in the set $\bar{PK} = \sum_{i=0}^N pk_i$. The function $KAg(pk)$ takes each public key $pk_i \in PK$ and decomposes it as $pk_i \leftarrow (y_i, \pi_i)$. It then calculates the aggregated public key \bar{PK} as the product of all y_i values in PK .

Signer S_i signs and assigns $C_i \leftarrow C_{i,j}$ as the set for the children in the spanning tree structure. parent signer P_i sign as S_i , while P^l serves as the root of the tree, also known as the leader. The signer $S_i \leftarrow \text{Sign}(PM, sk_i, m, \tau)$ executes the signature method in a tree τ using four distinct phases such as *initialisation*, *Commitment*, *Challenge*, and *Response*.

D. SIGNATURE PROCESSES

The overall signing process is illustrated in the flow diagram (shown in Figure 2) which is completed by initialisation, commitment, challenges, and response.

- **Initialisation:** Upon receiving an announcement message m , the leader P^l initiates the process of transmitting to children and commitment in a hierarchical

Algorithm 3 Signature Generation Steps

Require: Public parameters G, n , private key sk_i , message M , and other participants' commitments \tilde{V}_i , Public keys PK .

- 1: **Initialization:**
- 2: Each participant i generates a random scalar $v_i \in [1, n - 1]$.
- 3: Compute and share $V_i = v_i \cdot G$ to other users.
- 4: **Commitment Aggregation:**
- 5: Aggregate all intermediate points:
- 6: $V_{\text{agg}} = \sum_{i=1}^N V_i$.
- 7: **Challenge Generation:**
- 8: Compute the challenge e as:
- 9:

$$e = H(M, V_{\text{agg}}, \bar{PK})$$

where H is a secure cryptographic hash function, and pk_i is the public key of participant i .

- 10: **Response Computation:**
- 11: Each participant computes their partial signature:
- 12:

$$\tilde{s}_i = v_i + e \cdot sk_i \quad \text{mod } n.$$

- 13: Share \tilde{s}_i with other participants.
- 14: **Signature Aggregation:**
- 15: Aggregate all partial signatures to produce the final group signature:

$$\tilde{X}_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{s}_i \quad \text{mod } n$$

- 16: **Output:** Return the aggregated signature (\tilde{X}_i).

Algorithm 4 Signature Verification Process in MSS

Require: Aggregated signature (\tilde{X}_i), public parameters G, n , public keys PK , and message M .

- 1: Compute challenge $e = H(M, \tilde{X}_i, pk_1, pk_2, \dots, pk_N)$
- 2: Compute the aggregate public key: $PK = \sum_{i=1}^N pk_i$.
- 3: **Verify the Signature:** $\tilde{X}_i \cdot G = \tilde{X}_i + e \cdot (PK)$
- 4: **Output:**
- 5: **if** the ln 3' return ture **then**
- 6: The signature is **valid**.
- 7: **else**
- 8: The signature is **invalid**.
- 9: **end if**

tree structure. Each peer in the tree signs transaction proposal (S_i) and assign V_i a random secret value by raising g to the power of v_i and taking the result modulo 1. Consequently, S_i waits for the partial commitment \tilde{V}_{ij} of each immediate child j . After receiving all the partial commitments, S_i calculates \tilde{V}_i by multiplying all the \tilde{V}_{ij} values where j belongs to the set C_i .

- **Commitment:** The peer signature S_i selects a random secret value v_i and calculates V_i as g^{v_i} . Next, S_i awaits for \tilde{V}_{ij} , partial commitment, which is aggregated public key \tilde{X}_{ij} from each immediate child j . Upon receiving the partial commitments, S_i calculates \tilde{V}_i as the product of V_i and all \tilde{V}_{ij} where j belongs to C_i . Similarly, \tilde{X}_i is computed as the product of y_i and all \tilde{X}_{ij} where j belongs to C_i . Hence, the outcomes \tilde{V}_i and \tilde{X}_i are transmitted to their respective parent P_i , except when S_i is the leader (i.e., $i = 0$).

- **Challenge:**

When the partial commitment value of the immediate child is \tilde{V}_{0j} , the P^l computes the commitment $\tilde{V} = \tilde{V}_0 = V_0 \prod_j \tilde{V}_{0j}$. The joint signature's value c may be retained at P^l or sent to the verifier in advance. The total challenge can be computed as $c = H0(g_1, \tilde{V}, \tilde{X})$.

Through P^l , the challenge value c is passed back to its offspring.

- **Response:** The answer s_i is computed by the S_i using the formula $s_i = v_i \cdot c - e \cdot sk_i$, where e is computed as $H3(m)$ and c is computed as $H0(g_1, \tilde{V}, \tilde{X})$. After then, S_i awaits each partial response from its immediate children j , denoted as \tilde{s}_{ij} . The value of \tilde{s}_i is calculated by adding s_i to the sum of \tilde{s}_{ij} for each j in C_i after all responses that are partial have been received. The resultant \tilde{s}_i is then passed to its superior P_i , unless S_i is the leader (that is, $i = 0$). The collective signature (c, S) is ultimately produced by the leader P^l after computing the final response $S = \tilde{s}_0 = P^l + \sum_{j \in C_0} \tilde{s}_{0j}$.

E. OPERATIONAL STEPS

- 1) **Synchronization:** According to consensus policy, all endorsers $P_i^e (i = 1, \dots, N)$ can work as a subgroup (SG) in a consensus session τ . Group members are permitted to synchronise block information for $\text{Sign}(PM, (pk_i, sk_i), m, \tau)$. In the role of leader, user U generates an agreement challenge c using step 2 of $\text{Sign}(PM, (pk_i, sk_i), m, \tau)$. This challenge is then sent to each endorser as an element of the combined verification. In this section, $KAg(\bar{PK})$ is used to compute the aggregated public key \tilde{X} .
- 2) **Transaction Proposal:** In order to send the proposal m to the specified endorsers $P_i^e (i = 1, \dots, N)$ in an SG, the user U must first implement $\text{Sign}(PM, (pk_i, sk_i), m, \tau)$.
- 3) **Consensus:** Upon receiving a proposal from the user U , the endorser P_i^e verifies the user's identity by signature verification. It then uses its private key and the previous common challenge e to sign the transaction proposal while simulating the transaction execution. In the end, step 4 of $\text{Sign}(PM, (pk_i, sk_i), m, \tau)$ is completed by the endorser P_i^e by computing the partial response value s_i .
- 4) **Proposal Response:** $\text{Sign}(PM, (pk_i, sk_i), m, \tau)$ is approved by the endorsers $P_i^e (i = 1, \dots, N)$, who also return the proposal response P_i^e with an approval. The simulated transaction results and the partial answer values \tilde{s}_j are among the proposed responses that the user U gathers from children endorser j . Once all proposal responses are received, the U verifies the transaction outcomes and computes $S = \tilde{s}_u = s_u + \sum_{j \in e_u} \tilde{s}_j$. User U is able to provide a team signature $\tilde{X} = (e, S)$ that includes all of the chosen endorsers $P_i^e (i = 1, \dots, N)$ in addition to user U . Every peer, including user U , can readily authenticate this collective signature to see if it adheres to the endorsement policy.
- 5) **Transaction Submission:** The user U forwards the final transaction proposal and response to the leader P^l depending on the validity of the signature.
- 6) **Ledger Updated:** All the peers in the network are required to verify the signature using signature Algo-

gorithm 4 to accept the block before merging them into their chain.

IV. SECURITY ANALYSIS

A. THREAT MODEL

Suppose that there is an adversary \mathcal{A} aims to manipulate transaction M and fabricate the interactive signature. The adversary \mathcal{A} aims to create a counterfeit signature with a significant ϵ' value during a specific consensus session τ . The entity \mathcal{A}_m intercepts M from specific individuals who are acting honestly. In order to propagate M , it strategically deploys many Sybil nodes in the vicinity of the intended targets, assuming the guise of exchange nodes. The transformation \mathcal{A} modifies M to produce M_A , which is syntactically distinct but carries the same meaning.

Other reliable relaying nodes receive M_A from the Sybil nodes. When \mathcal{A} causes synchronisation limits, network delays, Sybil node usage, or other problems, M_A reaches a certain number of \mathcal{N}_{ps} nodes before M . In order to establish the interactive signature between U and \mathcal{N}_{ps} , \mathcal{A} is involved. This forgery of signatures occurs in the interactive incontestable signature scheme and is a probabilistic event that is guaranteed to occur in a polynomial amount of time. This risk model includes changes, manipulations, distribution, interactive signature forgery, and immediate verification of M_A before M can successfully carry out malleability attacks.

B. MULTI SIGNATURE FORKING PROTECTION

In this section, there are two key requirements that validate the security of the MSS method. Initially, to establish a MSS, a public and private key pairs (pk, sk) using $KG(\text{PM})$. Subsequently, a unified signature X on a transaction proposal m that signifies a group of signers in a tree τ using $Sign(\text{PM}, sk, m, \tau)$ is required.

Furthermore, it is important for a MSS to possess the quality of being unforgeable. The unforgeability of the proposed signature scheme system under current interactive attacks is demonstrated below.

Lemma 1: General Forking Lemma. Consider \mathcal{S} as a stochastic algorithm that incorporates randomness. When provided with the input $(x, r_1, \dots, r_q, \delta)$ and access to user U of size δ , where x is generated by the input generator IG , δ denotes \mathcal{S} 's random tape, and r_1, \dots, r_q are randomly selected values from Z_q , \mathcal{S} produces a pair (J, y) . Let π be the set of all vectors $(x, r_1, \dots, r_q, \delta)$. Define acc as the probability that \mathcal{S} can accurately produce the output (J, y) when provided with inputs $(x, r_1, \dots, r_q, \delta)$, where J is a non-empty subset of the set $\{1, \dots, q\}$.

The forking algorithm $F_{\mathcal{S}}(x)$ is shown as follows:

```

 $F_{\mathcal{S}}(x)$  :
Pick a random tape  $\delta$  for  $\mathcal{S}$ 
 $r_1, \dots, r_q \leftarrow U$ 
 $(J, y) \leftarrow \mathcal{S}(x, r_1, \dots, r_q, \delta)$ 
if  $J = 0$  then
    return  $(0, \perp, \perp)$ 
 $r'_1, \dots, r'_q \leftarrow U$ 
 $(J', y') \leftarrow \mathcal{S}(x, r'_1, \dots, r'_q, \delta)$ 
if  $J = J'$  and  $r_J \neq r'_J$ 
    return  $(1, y, y')$ 
else
    return  $(0, \perp, \perp)$ 

```

frk can be the probability $F_{\mathcal{S}}$ successfully outputs $(1, y, y')$ as shown below:

$$frk = \Pr[b = 1 : x \leftarrow IG; (b, y, y') \leftarrow F_{\mathcal{S}}(x)]. \quad (1)$$

So that we have:

$$frk \geq \text{acc} \left(\frac{\text{acc}}{q-1} \cdot \frac{1}{\delta} \right). \quad (2)$$

C. MALLEABILITY ATTACK

In the realm of signature schemes, malleability attacks are of great concern as they have the potential to compromise the security of the system by enabling an attacker to generate a legitimate signature for a related message, even without possessing the signer's private key. This could result in a range of security vulnerabilities, including message tampering, impersonation, or even a complete compromise of the protocol. We initially evaluate the security of our designs, specifically in relation to malleability attacks.

Theorem 1: Security of Malleability Attack: To keep security up against attacks that can be changed, U must stick to transaction implementations that have been approved using multi-signature schemes and $OUT_{\mathcal{S}}\text{script}^x$, and they must also add their own signatures.

Proof: Each user produces a value $hash_{ite} = H(\text{version} || \text{Tx}_{field} - \text{scriptSig as TxId}_2)$ during transaction (Tx). Tx will be completed by signing receiver (R). This is important to prove whether the Tx is signed by R when it is broadcasted to BCN. Let's assume, the honest nodes send two different values, $hash_{ite}$ and $hash'_{ite}$. Similarly r and r' represent the first trustworthy nodes that validate $hash_{ite}$ and $hash'_{ite}$ at moments t and t' respectively. When r approves $hash_{ite}$ at time t , it is necessary for r to broadcast $hash_{ite}$ at the same time t . Therefore, all truthful nodes that are connected to r (including r') must get $hash_{ite}$ no later than $t + 1 \leq t'$. Thus, it is impossible for r' to have generated $hash'_{ite} \neq hash_{ite}$ at t' , which creates a contradiction.

The correctness of the proposed MSS scheme is demonstrated via the verification equation, $\check{X}_i \cdot G = \check{X}_i + e \cdot PK$

which are presented in Algorithm 4, where \tilde{X}_i is the aggregated signature, R_{agg} is the aggregated intermediate point, e is the challenge, and PK is the aggregated public key. By substituting $\tilde{X}_i = \sum_{i=1}^N s_i$ and $PK = \sum_{i=1}^N p^{k_i}$, and using the fact that each participant computes $s_i = r_i + e \cdot sk_i$, the equation holds true due to the linearity of elliptic curve operations. This guarantees that the amalgamation of partial signatures and keys reliably generates a valid group signature that successfully undergoes the verification process. Incorporating a formal proof and an illustrative example in the paper unequivocally demonstrates that the scheme functions correctly for all valid inputs, so alleviating worries regarding its correctness.

V. EVALUATION AND ANALYSIS

The overall proposed scheme has been implemented in a simulated environment using Python 3.8, where we evaluated the overall value of Bitcoin by resembling the Bitcoin network. The network comprises 50 peers in a Docker container environment with connected internal transmission latency. The overall system comprises 100 processes across five machines, each equipped with 1.8GHz Intel Core i7-4790 processors and 128GB of 1600 MHz DDR3 RAM. Owners' nodes operate on an Intel i5 with 8GB DDR3, managing multiple threads. These machines are interconnected using a 1Gbps switch, providing a bandwidth of 1Gbps.

FIGURE 3: Required Time for Signature

A. MULTI-SIGNATURES PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The overall experiment uses RSA based signature algorithms as a baseline, including CoSi [40], Boneh–Lynn–Shacham (BLS) [41]. We have confirmed through tests that the length of a signature for RSA-based methods is 2048 bits. As shown in Figure 3, the BLS pairing action takes more of time both for signing and verifying in compare to CoSi and proposed MSS scheme. In contrast, even though the verification method requires more time, the needed time for MSS is extremely close to that of CoSi. The longer the

signature (for example, 2048 bits), the more storage space the system needs. According to the test results, for a valid signature length of 448 bits, CoSi and multisig have the fastest signing times and the slowest verification times. This is why CoSi and the proposed multi signature are able to strike the ideal balance between their coding complexity and memory requirements.

The comparison of calculation times for the signing and verification techniques is shown in Figure 4. It demonstrates that when the number of signers approaches 16384, the suggested schemes are extremely near to CoSi. We therefore assessed it at both the online and offline signing phases. While the offline signature phase happens during the commitment and challenge stages, the online signing phase happens during the announcement and response phases.

It is clear from the initial trial that the signature process takes almost the same amount of time in both MSS and CoSi. Due to the large amount of elliptic curve exponentiation involved, the offline signature process takes the longest. For this reason, the suggested approach's online signature component is quite effective. When 16384 signers are reached, it is observed that the suggested method's online signing time is less than 1 second, or about 1 percent of the signature algorithm's total operating time. The results of the CPU running are displayed in Figure 5.

The consensus in the signing algorithm means that the leader has to work more than the other signers. For this reason, more experiments have been conducted to determine the computational time required to calculate the leader node of the proposed MSS as well as CoSi in the signing procedure depicted in Figure 6. It is clear that ECDSA involves a great deal more complexity than scalar multiplication. The commitment and challenge stages can be precomputed using the suggested multi-signature approach, however CoSi requires that each phase be executed one after the other. Consequently, by solely taking into account the computation time on a leader node during the online signature phase, the suggested

FIGURE 4: Signature Execution and Verification

FIGURE 5: Executing time of Signing algorithm

FIGURE 6: Computation Time for Signature of a Leader at Consensus

method is more effective than CoSi.

B. MALLEABILITY ATTACK

We perform simulations of malleability attacks to evaluate the security and efficiency of MSS systems. To ensure simplicity, the PoW is consistently set at a difficulty level of $0 \times 19015 f 53$ throughout the rounds. In order to assess the resilience of Bitcoin wallets against malleability attacks, we manipulate the quantity of transactions, ranging from 1 to 50. We systematically adjust the number of queries from 1 to 50 to assess the latency and space overhead of various cryptocurrency protocols.

Figure 7 illustrates the effectiveness of the MA in safeguarding standard transactions during the implementation of MSS in standard transactions. The resistance level indicates the proportion of unsuccessful transactions caused by MA. The results indicate that the multi-signature system is highly reliable, with an almost 99% confirmation rate for honest

FIGURE 7: Malleability Defending

transactions. The proportion remains quite stable, fluctuating between 99.5% when $T_x = 20$ and 99.80% when $T_x = 50$. MSS provides a high level of protection against MA. It protects 15% higher than baseline signature schemes such as NInput and IIS.

In order to assess the level of resistance in contract transactions, we have implemented different signature schemes, including NInput, IIS, and the proposed MSS, individually within the deposit protocol. Figure 7 showcases the most resilient level of protection against malleability attacks in all transactions, achieved through the use of multi-signatures. For instance, when dealing with 30 transactions impacted by MT, multi-signature provides resistance to about 99.50% of malleable T's, surpassing NInput by 1.5 times. A method's practical significance has a significant impact on its success against machine translation. IIS demonstrates a mean resistance of 91% against MT in transactions, which is consistent with its intended architecture for particular protocols.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research proposes MSS to effectively combat malleability in both standard and contract transactions across cryptocurrency platforms. We have evaluated and simulated the proposed signature scheme for fast-clearing transactions on a blockchain network. In contrast to CoSi, the most widely used multi-signature scheme that utilises Schnorr signatures, these approaches accomplish increased online efficiency and security. This ensures secure, immediate transaction confirmations and allows for comparisons with leading malleability solutions, signature schemes, as well as deposit and commit protocols. The signature scheme performs 1.5 times faster for approval than NInput and protects malleability in digital currency within the DiFi system.

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